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Involvement of Selected Church Denominations in Drug Abuse Prevention Among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State

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Abstract

In Nigeria, varying rates of drug abuse among adolescents have been reported. This study therefore investigated into the involvement of the church in adolescent drug abuse so as to curb a furtherance of this social malaise among Nigerian adolescents. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The target population for the study included: members and ministers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith Church (LFC), Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) and Baptist Church, all in Ede South Local Government Area (ESLGA). A sample size of fifteen respondents was randomly selected from each of the four churches to ensure that the population of the study has an equal chance of being picked which totalled sixty (60) participants in all. The research

instrument used for this research was a questionnaire. Percentage and frequency counts were adopted to analyse the data collected for the study. According to the findings of the study, causes of drug abuse include peer pressure, various malfunctioning familial dynamics, media influence, and so on. The study further established that drug abuse can lead to: addiction, various physical health complications, and so on. Regular workshops and seminars are the various forms of church involvement preventing drug abuse among adolescents. These various programmes of the church are obstructed by stigma and denial, resource constraints, and traditional practices, To address these challenges, programme organizers were counselled to engage in community sensitization efforts and adapt the programmes to the cultural and social context of Ede, Osun State.

Keywords: Drug Abuse, Adolescent, Church Involvement, Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State

Introduction

In Nigeria, varying rates of drug abuse among adolescents have been reported. For instance, in the South-East region, the prevalence rate of any substance use among high school students was 32.9%, with alcohol being the most used substance (with 29.0% of users), and cocaine being the least used (2.1%) (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). In the South-West region, from 15.0% to 69.3% of adolescents were reported using any psychoactive substances, including local substances such as kola nut. These data presentation from a previous study shows an outrageous increased rate of the involvement of adolescents from the South-West in drug abuse. Thus, adolescents from the South-West of Nigeria, especially, those in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State need to be rescued, and the church should be at the forefront of such a rescue mission.

The term "adolescence" originates from the Latin word "*adolescere*" which means "to grow up" or "to nature." It is a phase of life that signifies the transition from childhood to adulthood and involves numerous physical and psychological changes. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescence is a period between the ages of 10-19, characterized by emotional, psychosocial, and behavioural changes, which lead to the transformation from childhood to adulthood.

Currently, approximately one-third of the world's population falls within the age range of 10-24, and four out of five young people reside in developing countries. This percentage is expected to increase to 87% by the year 2020.

Adolescents are the population under study within this age bracket. An adolescent is an individual who has outgrown the social status of a child but has not yet been granted the social and mature privileges of an adult. They are neither a child nor a grown-up. In certain cultures, an individual's maturity is defined by the role they play. Moreover, there are variations in who is considered an adolescent, even within a single culture.

Adolescence is a critical period as it is marked by several physical, psychological, and social changes, and signifies the move from childhood to adulthood. (Olugbenga-Bello; Adebimpe; Abodurin, 2009). Adolescence is a time of experimentation, exploration, curiosity, and identity search which also involves the use and abuse of psychoactive substances. These drugs apply their major effects on the brain, resulting in sedation, encouragement, or changes in mood. Adolescence is a challenging stage of life for most individuals and often marks the onset of many unhealthy behaviours, including drug misuse. (Birhanu, Bisetegn, & Woldeyohannes, 2014). Several factors put adolescents at risk of substance use, including increased adventurous tendencies, peer influences, and risk-taking behaviour (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). Substance use also has negative impacts on families and communities, with costly social, physical, and mental health consequences. (Russell, Simpson, Flannery & Ohannessian, 2019).

According to the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC (2001), a drug is a chemical substance that has an impact on the body or the higher nervous system and is distinct from foodstuff in its ability to influence the structure or function of an organism. As stated by the World Health Organisation (WHO, 1967), drugs can modify the functions of living organisms and may be used for therapeutic or recreational purposes. In the context of biological function, a drug is a substance that possesses the ability to induce chemical actions that result in changes to perceptions, cognition, mood, behaviour, and general physiological processes (Okoye, 2001). It is therefore regarded as a chemical modifier of living tissues that can elicit psychological and behavioural changes, as explained by Nnachi (2007).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines "a drug" as "any substance, solid, liquid or gas that changes the function or structure of the body in some way" while the term substance is "any product that affects the way people feel, think, see, taste, smell, hear, or behave" (UNODC.). The phenomenon

of drug abuse has been characterized as the utilization of any substance to the point of adverse health effects or impairment of societal functioning (Edlin, Golanty, and Brown, 2000). Substance abuse, on the other hand, is a broad term that refers to the use of any substance—illegal drugs, prescription drugs, over-the-counter (OTC) drugs or alcohol—in excessive amounts (Pallavi Suyog Uttekar, & Jasmine Shaikh, 2021). Often, the term “substance use” is preferred, so that all things that affect the way a person feels, thinks, sees, tastes, smells, hears and behaves are included. Thus, glue is a substance used by many street children and methamphetamines are substances used by many young people who go to discos and bars (Pallavi Suyog Uttekar, & Jasmine Shaikh 2021). Drugs commonly implicated in abuse are referred to as drugs of abuse, and their misuse is associated with various issues, especially among young people. Extensive research has shown that alcohol, tobacco, and marijuana are the most frequently abused drugs among adolescents in many societies (Lennox & Cecchini, 2008; Makanjuola, Daramola, & Obembe, 2007).

The consequences of drug abuse are far-reaching and include social vices such as rape, robbery, and sexual promiscuity (World Health Organization, 2003). Lennox and Cecchini (2006) established a strong correlation between drug use and sociability, rebelliousness, and deviant behaviour. The problem of drug abuse is a global epidemic that has continued to spread due to the ease of adopting vices by humans. The World Health Organization estimates that 76.3 million people worldwide suffer from alcohol use disorder (Putul, 2011). By the end of the 20th century, approximately 185 million people globally over the age of 15 years were involved in the use of drugs (WHO, 2017). The reality is that the more the number of people engaging in drug abuse, the more the likelihood of addiction as drug use is the first step to addiction.

Adolescents often depend on various substances such as tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, heroin, alcohol, ephedrine, caffeine, glue, and barbiturates, among others, for their daily activities, including social, educational, political, and moral activities (Oshikoya & Alli, 2006). Dependence and addiction are among the major consequences of drug abuse among adolescents in Nigeria (Oshikoya & Alli, 2006). Experimentation with drugs during adolescence is common, as young people often use drugs for various reasons, such as curiosity, pleasure, stress reduction, or to feel more grown up.

The impact of drug abuse among adolescents has been regarded as a moral decadence. This is because it has caused physical damage to the adolescents and brought shame to society, as they are intentionally and unlawfully using drugs (Eze and Omeje, 1999). Many adolescents are dependent on drugs for their daily activities and cannot function without them. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), drugs such as alcohol and tobacco have caused more road accidents and claimed more lives than any other sickness suffered by mankind. The global drug trafficking industry is on the rise, while international cooperation against drug trafficking is lacking organization and strength (Okeke, 2004). Despite the significant negative consequences of substance abuse on the health and well-being of adolescents, studies continue to report high rates of substance use among this population. Different rates and patterns of substance use have been reported depending on the country where such a study was carried out (Adeloye, Olawole-Isaac, Auta, Dewan, Omoyele, and Ezeigwe, 2019). For instance, in the US, alcohol was reported as the most used substance, with 72.5% of users, followed by cigarettes (46.3%) and marijuana (36.8%) (Feinstein Richter, & Foster, 2012). In Ethiopia, the lifetime prevalence of any substance use was 65.4%, while current substance use among adolescents was 47.9%. Alcohol was the most used drug, with a lifetime and current prevalence of 59% and 40.9%, respectively (Birhanu, Bisetegn, & Woldeyohannes, 2014).

In Nigeria, varying rates have been reported. In the South-East region, for example, the prevalence rate of any substance use among high school students was 32.9%, with alcohol being the most used substance (with 29.0% of users), and cocaine being the least used (2.1%) (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). In the South-West region, from 15.0% to 69.3% of adolescents were reported using any psychoactive substances, including local substances such as kola nut. Alcohol remains the most consumed substance, followed by cigarettes. However, the pattern seems to be changing, with tramadol being the second most abused substance (Idowu, Aremu, Olumide, & Ogunlaja, 2018).

As the 2018 National Drug Use Survey revealed, in Nigeria at that time there were around 14.3 million drug users of which close to 3 million suffered from a drug use disorder. The World Drug Report further noted that in the last 24 years' cannabis potency had increased by as much as four times in parts of the world, even as the percentage of adolescents who

perceived the drug as harmful fell by as much as 40 per cent, despite evidence that cannabis use is associated with a variety of health and other harms, especially among regular long-term users. Recent research shows that 15-20 percent of drug addicts in Ede are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent (Adeloju, 2021). Drug abuse among youths in Nigeria is now a common phenomenon. Females are not exempt in this evil act. A recent research shows that 15-20 percent of drug addicts are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent, Drug use among youth is one of challenging social problems facing Ede, Osun State, drug abuse has contributed negatively to the social and economic development in all comprising of traders, students, unskilled workers and the unemployed as shown by a retrospective study carried out by NDLEA (Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency).

Drug education pertains to the endeavour of imparting knowledge to individuals residing in a locality where psychoactive substances may be readily accessible and possess a significant impact on the well-being of families, politics, and finances. Its fundamental aim is to educate individuals on the adverse effects of drugs on physical health. Besides contributing to the prevention of substance abuse, drug education plays a pivotal role in offering secure and wholesome resources that advocate healthy living. Additionally, drug education strives to enlighten adolescents on the potential harm associated with all drugs, whether legal or illegal, and elucidates that the drug experience is contingent on multifarious factors, encompassing the individual, the substance, and the environment (Aspen Ridge, 2021).

Adolescent substance utilization continues to be a prominent worry on a global scale, presenting severe health, societal, and monetary impediments. Various establishments, such as academic institutions, households, and faith-based groups, have assumed the responsibility of instructing adolescents about the hazards of drug misuse in response to this predicament. The burden of this study, therefore, is to shed light on the roles of the church in providing drug education to adolescents.

Statement of the Problem

The alarming rate at which adolescents engage in drug abuse is a cause for concern. It is a social menace which has caused several havocs to the society. Despite this, several youths still romance with it. A lot of psychiatric

hospitals in Nigeria are full of youths who are receiving psycho-therapeutic treatment. The percentage of insane youths is greater than that of the old people, due to drug abuse. Some youths are school dropouts, again, due to their involvement in drug and its ill-consequences. Calling attention to the aftermath of menace generally, Dairo (2014) opined that the African man's actions and behaviour must not precipitate calamity for him, his family and for his society at large. Also, due to the same factor, a lot of Nigerian youths have become homeless, wanderers, derelicts, unemployed, rapist, thugs, armed robbers and so on. A lot of young people's lives and property in Nigeria have also been wasted in accident and violence because of drug. Again, for the same reason, youths who should be the hope of their families and the larger society; youths, who should be useful to themselves have killed themselves prematurely. According to a recent research, 15-20 percent of drug addicts are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent. These include traders, students, unskilled workers and the unemployed as shown by a retrospective study carried out by NDLEA (Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency).

Research Methods

This section deliberates upon the intricacies of the research design, delineates the precise population of interest in the study, explicates the sample and sampling techniques employed, scrutinizes the validity of the research instrument, elucidates the administration of the instrument and elucidates the method of data analysis. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. This gave a clear picture of the population and provided detailed information about the population. The target population for this study include Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith Church (LFC), Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) and Baptist Church respectively. A sample size of fifteen respondents was selected from each of the four churches. The respondents included members, ministers, and workers of the selected churches. A simple random method was used to ensure that the population of the study has an equal chance of being picked. In all, a sample of sixty (60) participants was used for the study. Since the respondents were from the body of Christ, the samples were treated as homogeneous.

The research instrument used for this research was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A of the instrument

consisted of the respondents' biodata while section B consisted of variables that were related to the subject matter. The questionnaire was structured in form of a four-point Likert scale coded as follows: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly Disagreed (SD) and Disagreed (D).

The researcher assistants met the respondents one-on-one. He also took the pain, right from the outset, to explain essential issues about their involvement in the research which included the anonymity of their responses, the need for objectivity and sincerity while filling the questionnaire. This enabled them to explain certain items on the questionnaire to the respondents so that the questionnaire would be properly filled. Besides, they were advised to work independently. The respondents were then given enough time to fill their copies after which, they were collected on the spot. This method ensured correct completion and a high percentage return of the completed copies of the questionnaire.

The information gathered was analysed based on individual responses to the questions. The percentage and frequency count were adopted to analyse the data to be collected for the study.

Data Presentation

Demographic Tables

Sixty (60) respondents were used as sample for this study and their responses were used for data analysis.

Table 4.1 Respondent's Denomination

Denomination	Respondent	Percentage (%)
RCCG	15	25.86
LFC	15	25.86
Baptist	15	22.41
CAC	15	25.86
Total	60	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 4.1, it is obvious that fifteen (15) of the participants came from RCCG, fifteen (15) of them were from LFC, 15 of them were from the Baptist Church while the remaining fifteen (15) came from CAC.

Table 4.1.1 Respondent’s Academic Level

Academic Level	Respondent	Percentage (%)
SSCE	10	17.24
ND/NCE	18	31.03
HND/BSC.	22	37.03
MSC/PhD	01	1.7
Total	51	85

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1 showcases the academic qualifications of the participants. While the table shows that all of them were educated, it also shows that majority 22(37.03%) of them had either HND or BSc. This reflects that all of them had the intellectual capacity to provide the information required. However, it should be noted that nine (9) of them did not provide information about their academic qualification.

Reponses to Research Questions:

Table 4.2.1 Causes of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	S/A	A	SD	D
1.	Adolescents abuse drugs due to peer influence	44 (73.33%)	16 (26.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
2.	Adolescents are involved in drug abuse to attain a sense of euphoria, that is to ‘feel high’	39 (65%)	20 (33.33%)	1 (1.67%)	0 (0%)

3. Adolescents are involved in drug abuse as a result of lack of parental care and guidance.	31 (51.67%)	23 (38.33%)	3 (1.67%)	5 (8.33%)
4. Adolescents are involved in drug abuse as a result of stress, anxiety, depression, and pain.	31(51.67%)	25(46.67%)	3(5%)	1(1.67%)
5. Adolescents are also involved in drug abuse as a result of single parent or divorced parent.	26(43.33%)	31(51.67%)	2(3.3%)	1(1.67%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.1 shows that drug abuse among adolescents is caused by various factors like peer influence as unanimously attested to by all the respondents used for this study. The 100% agreement by the respondents shows that peer influence is a strong factor that leads to drug abuse among adolescents. Also, as attested to by majority 59 (98%) of the participants identified desire for euphoria as one of the causes of drug abuse among adolescents. Lack of parental care and guidance is another factor leading to adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as attested to by majority 54 (90%) of the participants. Emotional impairment is another major cause for adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as agreed on by majority 56 (98.34%). Lastly, majority 57 (95%) of the participants agreed that

adolescents are involved in drug abuse because of single parent or divorced parent.

Table 4.2.2 Effects of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in some Church Denominations in Ede South Local Government Area

S/N	Statement	S/A	A	SD	D
1.	Adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression	39(65%)	21(35%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
2.	Adolescent drug abusers are usually vulnerable to different forms of physical, spiritual and mental health complications.	33(55%)	27(45%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
3.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually commit suicide	26 (43.33%)	32 (53.33)	0(0%)	2(3.3%)
4.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc	25 (41.6%)	33 (55%)	1 (1.67)	1(1.67)
5.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually end up as school drop-outs.	22(36.6%)	29(48.3 3%)	2(33%)	1 (1.67%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.2 presents the effects of drug abuse among adolescents in Ede. Majority, 60 (100%) of the respondents agreed that adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression. Vulnerability to different forms of physical, spiritual and mental health complications is also an aftermath of adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as attested to unanimously by all 60 (100%) of the participants. Majority, 58 (96.66%) of the respondents asserted that drug abusers commit suicide. Also, majority, 58 (96.66%) asserted that drug abusers usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc. Lastly, majority, 51(85%) opined that adolescent drug abusers usually end up as school drop-outs.

Table 4.2.3: Ways in Which the Church is Involved in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescent in Ede Local Government Area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1	My church organises regular workshops and seminars to educate youths and adolescents on drug issues	19(33.66%)	26 (43.33%)	6 (10%)	9(15%)
2	My church partners with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and	19(33.66%)	25 (41.6%)	8 (13.3%)	8(13.8%)

	adolescents on drug abuse				
3	My church provides counseling and therapy for those who are involved in drug abuse	17(26.67%)	30(50%)	6(!0%)	8(13.8%)
4	My church provides materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse	18 (30%)	31(51.67%)	4(6.6%)	7(11.6%)
5	My church helps people, especially, adolescents, within and outside RCCG to overcome drug-related issues	19(31.66%)	18 (30%)	4 (6.6%)	9(15%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.3 presents various ways in which the church is involved in drug abuse prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area. First, majority, 45 (76.99%) attested to the fact that their churches organise regular workshops and seminars to educate youths and adolescents on drug issues. Also, according to the data available on the table, majority, 44 (73.26%) of the respondents agreed that their churches partner with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and adolescents on drug abuse. Furthermore, 47 (76.67%) of the participants, agreed that their churches provide counseling and therapy

for those who are involved in drug abuse. In addition, majority, 49 (81.67%) of the participants acknowledged that their churches provide materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse. Lastly, 37 (61.66%) of the respondents agreed that their churches help people, especially, Christian and non-Christian adolescents, to overcome drug-related issues.

Table 4.2.4: Challenges limiting the involvement of some church Denomination in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1.	Drug abuse prevention programmes adopted by my church are obstructed by stigma and denial.	20(33.33%) 43(71.66%)	23(38.33%)	7(11.6%)	9(15%)
2.	Drug abuse prevention measures adopted by my church are also limited by cultural norms and traditional practices.	31(51.67%) 47(78.34%)	16(26.67%)	4(6.6%)	9(15%)
3.	Religious diversity is another obstacle to the drug abuse prevention measures adopted by my church.	30(50%) 49(81.66%)	19(31.66%)	5(8.33%)	6(10%)
4.	Parental involvement also has its own way of limiting the	37(61.66%) 54(89.99%)	17(28.33%)	3(5%)	3(5%)

	measures adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.				
5.	Lack of commitment and manpower also has its own limiting effects on the strategies adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.	20(33.33%) 52(85.66%)	32(52.33%)	4(6.6%)	3(5%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.4 depicts the challenges limiting the efforts of the church in combating drug abuse as 43 (71.66%) of the participants opined that the strategies are obstructed by stigma and denial. 47 (78.34%) of the respondents also said that the strategies are also limited by cultural norms and traditional practices. 47 (78.34%) of them further identified cultural norms and traditional practices as limiting factors to the efforts of the church in combating drug abuse among adolescents in Ede. Parental involvement is another limitation to the efforts of the church in fighting drug related issues as attested to cumulatively by 54 (89.99%) of the participants. Lastly, lack of commitment and manpower also limit the success of the endeavours of the church concerning drug abuse as attested to by 52 (85.66%) of the participants.

Table 4.2.5: Solutions to the Challenges Limiting the Involvement of some Church Denominations in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1.	My church should redesign its drug abuse	33(55%)	23(37.3%)	2(3.3%)	2 (3.3%)

	prevention programmes for adolescents in such a way that helpes will not be victims of stigma and denial of access to existing facilities.	56(93.3 3%)	8.33 %)		
2.	The programmes should be sensitive to the cultures of the land and the adolescents.	27(45%) 57(75%)	30(5 0%)	2(3.3 %)	1 (1.67%)
3.	The programmes should be sensitive to the religious diversity of the land.	27(45%) 56(93.3 3%)	29(4 8.33 %)	2(3.3 %)	1 (1.67%)
4.	Parents must be properly counselled so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.	32(53.3 3%) 58(96.6 6%)	26(4 3.33 %)	1(1.6 7%)	1 (1.67%)
5.	My church must use qualified, competent and committed officers for its drug abuse prevention programmes in an attempt to reach out to the adolescents under its care.	37(61.6 6%) 57(94.9 9%)	20(3 3.33 %)	3(5%)	0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.5 reflects the attempts that the church can adopt to subdue the challenges limiting her efforts as 56(93.33%) suggested that the church should be culture sensitive; 56(93.33%) of them counselled the church to be conscious of the religious diversity that characterized the land; 58(96.66%)

counselled the church to properly counsel parents so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes and 57(94.99%) advised the church to make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.

Discussion

Factors Influencing Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State

The findings of this study depicts that adolescents are involved in drug abuse in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State due to some reasons like peer influence as attested to by 60(100%) of the respondents. In consonance with this, Adebisi et al (2017), opined that adolescents frequently succumb to the influence of their peers, which can prompt them to partake in drug experimentation in order to assimilate or attain social acceptance within their peer group. Desire for euphoria as acknowledged by 59(98%) of the respondents is another cause of adolescents involvement in drug abuse. This is corroborated by Okafor (2020), who explicated that euphoria, that is, the general feeling of ‘getting high’ is always associated with drug abuse. The study also identified lack of parental care and guidance as one of the causes of drug abuse as agreed on by 54(90%). Establishing this assertion in an elaborate manner, Adebisi et al., (2017), said that malfunctioning familial dynamics, including parental substance abuse, neglect, or inadequate supervision, can contribute to the susceptibility of adolescents to drug abuse. The study further recognized emotional impairment as a cause of drug abuse as attested to by 56(98.34%). Supporting this idea, Adebisi et al., (2017) opined that underlying mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, or trauma can heighten the propensity for drug abuse among adolescents who seek relief or escape. Lastly, single or divorced parent can also push adolescents into drug abuse as attested to by 57(95%) of the respondents. This is in line with the opinion of Adebisi et al, 2017 as he also identified parental neglect and inadequate supervision by parents as major causes that heighten drug abuse among adolescents.

Consequences of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede, Osun State

The consequences of substance misuse among young individuals in Ede, Osun State, Nigeria, have profound and wide-ranging implications on their

physical, mental, social, and academic well-being. Majority, 60(100%) of the respondents claimed that adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression. This correlates with the opinion of Adeloye & Odeigah, (2014) that substance abuse is linked to an augmented vulnerability to mental health disorders, such as depression, anxiety, and schizophrenia. Suicidal attempts are also very common among adolescent drug abusers as attested to by the majority, 58(96.66%) of the respondents used for this study. In agreement with this, Ayomide & Ayomide, (2023), identified suicide as one of the major consequences of drug abuse. Drug abusers also usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc as attested to by 58(96.66%) of the respondents. In line with the findings of this study, Ayomide & Ayomide (2023) identified erratic behaviour as one of the consequences of drug abuse. Lastly, this study found out that drug abusers usually experience school discontinuation and this view is shared by (Adeloye & Odeigah, 2014) when he says that substance misuse may lead to dropping out of school, curtailing educational and career opportunities.

Measures Adopted by the Church to Prevent Adolescents' Involvement in Drug Abuse in Ede South Local Government Area

Involvement in and commitment to diaconal services, including prevention of drug abuse among adolescents, are apparent features of most Nigerian churches including RCCG, Baptist, LFC and CAC. Corroborating this, Adedibu (2023) said that the missional obligation of the church requires spiritual renewal, socio-economic reformation of people and the community through its religious teachings and belief system. He said further that the missionary endeavour of the church all over various cultural frontiers to initiate and retain churches is basically transformational. One of such transformational services is helping people to be immune against drug abuse or recover from it if they has already been trapped into it. Adding to the debate, Dairo (2012) opined that today's church is opening up space for the Holy Spirit to move powerfully in the lives of the faithful in the ministry of healing including the healing of the mind that has been captured by drug abuse. The pertinent question now is: how can the church help the individuals and the society at large to rise above drug abuse? To answer this question, this study proposed the following: a) organising workshops and seminars as suggested by 45(76.99%) of the respondents, b) partnering

with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and adolescents on drug abuse as suggested by 44(73.26%) of the respondents, c) providing counseling and therapy for those who are involved in drug abuse as suggested by 47(76.67%) d) providing materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse as suggested by 49(81.67%) of the participants and e) helping people, especially, Christian and non-Christian adolescents, to overcome drug-related issues as opined by 37(61.66%) of the respondents.

Factors Limiting the Endeavours of the Church in Combating Drug Abuse

As committed as the church is in combating drug abuse among adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State, certain factors are standing as obstacles. These obstacles include: stigma and denial, as attested to by 43(71.66%) of the participants. This is because church-based support may further enhance stigmas that link drug abuse with sinfulness. These stigmas may absolutely hinder abusers from seeking support (Armstrong, 2025). Cultural norms and traditional practices also have a way of limiting the efforts of the church in mitigating drug abuse. Supporting this, Monari et al., (2024) opined that culturally rooted beliefs surrounding substance abuse have a deep impact on family subtleties in communities. These culturally rooted beliefs, at times, deter the church in her effort to mitigate drug abuse as attested to by 47(78.34%). Religious diversity also plays a limiting role to the church as an agent of mitigation against drug abuse as identified by 47(78.34%). Nigeria, including Ede in Osun State, exhibits religious diversity, with different religious groups potentially holding distinct perspectives on drug abuse and the role of the church in addressing this issue. (Odejide, 2006). Parental involvement is another limitation to the efforts of the church in fighting drug related issues as attested to cumulatively by 54(89.99%) of the participants. Engaging parents and caregivers in the programmes like this may prove challenging due to their work commitments and other responsibilities. (Adebiyi et al., 2017) Lastly, lack of commitment and manpower as opined by 52(85.66%) of the respondents also reduce the role of the church in assisting drug abusers.

Solutions to the Challenges Limiting the Involvement of some Church Denominations in Ede Local Government Area

To address these challenges, 56 (93.33%) of the respondents suggested that the church should be culture sensitive; 56(93.33%) of them counselled the church to be conscious of the religious diversity that characterized the land; 58 (96.66%) counselled the church to properly counsel parents so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes and 57(94.99%) advised the church to make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.

Conclusion

The study has established that drug abuse is a menace that is rampant among adolescents in Ede South Local Government, Ede, Osun State. The study has also found out that there are factors influencing this social vice. Worst of all, the study identified some terrible repercussions of this menace. To address the vice, churches in the local government represented by RCCG, LFC, Baptist and CAC rose to the occasion. However, the measures taken by these churches were confronted by certain constraints; hence, the study proposed some solutions that will beef up the efforts of the church to mitigate adolescents' involvement in drug abuse in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State.

Recommendations

The study then recommends that the church should:

1. Foster close collaboration with local leaders, engage in community sensitization efforts and adapt her anti-drug abuse programmes to the cultural and social context of Ede, Osun State.
2. Pay close attention to multi-religious nature of Ede, Osun State
3. Collaborate with parents so as to get the best result from them
4. Make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.
5. Embark on community motivation, encouragement and outreaches to enlighten member of the society on the imminent dangers related to drug abuse.
6. Ensure cooperation among the entire body of Christ if the social menace is to be conquered.
7. Display fairness among the adolescents in promoting shared ethical values, and institutional reforms in the society.

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8. Collaborate with government, private rehabilitation centres and the NGOs should join forces with the church denomination to minimize or even eradicate drug abuse.

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